

INFLUENCE OF E-LEARNING ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY IN EBONYI STATE

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of this study is to determine the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology in Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State. The design of the study was descriptive survey. Three research questions and one null hypothesis was posed; tested at 0.05 level of significance. The participants of the study were drawn from students in the Faculty of Education, Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State and the sample size of 80 male and female students offering Educational Technology was selected from two (2) departments in the Faculty of Education, Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State using a purposive sampling technique. A self-structured questionnaires titled: E-Learning and Academic Performance Questionnaire (EAPQ) was developed, validated and used for the study. The internal consistency reliability of the instruments was ascertained using Cronbach Alpha procedure and reliability estimate of 0.82 was obtained for EAPQ. The questionnaires were administered by hand with the help of 5 trained research assistants and all the copies were returned. The data obtained from data collection were analyzed using mean and standard to answer the research questions and t-test for the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the data collected and analyzed, the study revealed that e-learning influences positively the academic performance of students in Educational Technology in Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State, as this e-learning sites makes it easier for students to access more teaching materials than ever before. It was therefore recommended among others that government should positively demonstrate more serious attitude to the use of e-learning strategies in schools with the provision of adequate funding and its facilities for effective use.

Keywords: E- learning, Academic Performance, Educational Technology, Students, Universities

INTRODUCTION

Education is a continuously changing and developing process. As a changing process, it cultivates the child in response to evolving circumstances and times, and as a developing process, it progresses systematically. A key element of this system is Technology. Timi (2020) suggests that technology by itself will not significantly impact student outcomes; instead, it must be integrated comprehensively and consistently to fundamentally alter how individuals – specifically students – learn. E-learning refers to the application of electronic technologies to access educational content beyond the traditional

face-to-face learning framework. This learning is perpetually delivered over the internet. According to Schmidt (2005), e-learning encompasses traditional training methods, including courses, on-the-spot training, chosen learning resources, formal organization through document repositories, and community building achieved through social software. The rise of e-learning programs, as noted by Lockwood and Gooley (2002), is propelled by the demand for more affordable educational methods, enhanced access to information, effective learning experiences, and increased flexibility. Stephenson (2001) suggests that there is limited systematic research regarding the overall effectiveness of e-learning as an educational medium, despite considerable interest in the topic. Stephenson recognizes that although much remains to be explored, various e-learning courses focused on achieving sustainable development have been created, showcasing e-learning's potential to influence thousands, if not millions, of individuals and possibly inspire change. Given the developing nature of e-learning and the lack of substantial evidence regarding its educational benefits, a collective understanding of what constitutes e-learning is being established.

E-learning can be described as the integration of learning with technology (Okah, 2009; Okah, 2010). It is instruction delivered via solely digital technologies like CD ROMs, the internet, and private networks (Dewar & Whittington, 2000). Olele and Nwabueze (2015) agree that the digital resources accessible in higher education institutions include E-books across various fields, E-journals for different subjects, UNESCO publications, E-encyclopedias, CD-ROMs for multiple Science disciplines, CD-ROMs for various Social Science subjects, CD-ROMs for different Humanities topics, and computer workstations linked to the internet. E-Learning is also referred to as online learning or electronic learning. Utilizing information and communication technology to enhance teaching and learning is known as E-learning (Oye, Salleh & Lahad, 2012). From Salehudin et al. (2021)'s perspective, E-learning includes group learning on social media platforms such as WhatsApp, Telegram, Zoom, or other social media to facilitate simultaneous learning across diverse locations. E-learning is viewed as an innovative method for delivering educational services via electronic means in a manner that improves students' knowledge, skills, and other outcomes (Fazlollahtabar & Muhammadzadeh, 2012). The e-learning system is executed through a network connection. It constitutes a form of learning employing information and communication technology via a computer or laptop connected to the internet (Horton & Horton, 2003). E-learning can also be defined as learning facilitated through a computer or laptop connected to an internet network. Raouna (2023) identified several e-learning platforms: Udemy: Udemy strongly aims to disrupt and democratize the educational landscape by enabling anyone to learn from its extensive network of more than 20000 Subject Matter Experts. To a significant degree, Udemy has achieved its mission. This eLearning platform provides a variety of content creation tools, including PDF documents, PowerPoint presentations, and allows users to combine text and video content to develop and publish courses. Coursera: As one of the leading providers of massive open online courses, Coursera collaborates with universities and organizations globally to offer a diverse array of in-depth courses, both free and paid, to learners worldwide. Coursera boasts one of the largest sets of university partners, courses, specializations, and degree programs available; LinkedIn Learning: formerly known as Lynda, LinkedIn Learning is one of the premier online learning platforms, featuring a vast array of courses and a tutorial library that encompasses subjects in business, creativity, and technology. Other e-learning platforms like Skillshare, edX, and Udacity also provide unique advantages and disadvantages (Raouna, 2023). These platforms can be embraced by higher education institutions as effective online learning solutions to address the gaps created by traditional learning methods, such as in-person classes.

The recent outbreak of the Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) highlighted the undeniable impact of e-learning on student learning outcomes. Many schools and educational institutions faced interruptions in their academic activities due to

the complete shut-down aimed at preventing the virus's spread. During this time, learning and academic activities progressed in certain institutions globally, albeit through electronic platforms. The adverse effects of the COVID-19 pandemic were mitigated by educational establishments that had robust e-learning systems in place during the peak of the crisis. E-learning platforms such as Udemey, LinkedIn Learning, Coursera, Microsoft Teams, Zoom, and WhatsApp were used by both faculty and students at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Federal College of Education Technical Umunze, and Federal Polytechnic Oko to maintain their usual teaching and learning processes during the COVID-19 lockdowns, thereby reducing the negative consequences of extended closures on their academic performance. Academic performance refers to measuring student achievements across different subjects. It encompasses factors such as intellectual capacity, personality traits, motivation levels, skills, interests, study habits, self-esteem, and the quality of teacher-student interactions. A favorable outcome on a student's academic performance indicates a successful teaching and learning experience, provided that all other factors remain unchanged. Olufemi (2018) noted that various factors affect students' academic performance, including learning capabilities, parental influence, peer impact, the quality of teaching, and the availability of learning resources.

Moreover, Onyema et al. (2020) confirmed that technology has transformed teachers' methods from traditional approaches—in which they primarily dispense knowledge—to more flexible methods where they function as facilitators, mentors, and motivators, encouraging student participation and learning. The impact of online e-learning platforms on academic performance has been a topic of current interest among researchers and scholars. Many academics contend that students in higher education institutions who engage in e-learning typically achieve better results than those participating in face-to-face classes. Holley (2002) discovered that students engaged in online E-Learning tend to achieve higher grades compared to those who follow traditional teaching methods. Consequently, numerous higher education institutions are adopting online e-learning platforms, commonly referred to as virtual learning. Conversely, some researchers argue that e-learning platforms do not enhance the teaching and learning processes within universities (Fayomi, Ayo, Ajayi & Okorie, 2015). This may be attributed to a lack of research on the effects of e-learning platforms on students' academic performance. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the impact of e-learning on the academic performance of students in Educational Technology, specifically at Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Universities are founded to provide students with both practical and intellectual skills, making them capable and valuable members of society. They play a crucial role in national development by enhancing and diversifying their programs to cultivate skilled personnel in line with national needs. To achieve this goal, it is imperative to ensure that instructional mediums, such as e-learning, are utilized effectively and efficiently within universities. Furthermore, the success of e-learning in Nigerian universities would be facilitated by the availability of functional e-learning resources. However, many universities struggle to utilize e-learning effectively, resulting in poor learning outcomes and consequently high failure rates in both internal and external assessments. This challenge may stem from inadequate learning facilities within Nigerian universities. Thus, there is a pressing need to evaluate the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of students in Educational Technology at Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study was to examine the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology in Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ebonyi State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. identify types of e-learning platforms available for use among Educational Technology students
2. examine the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology
3. determine common challenges associated with use of e-learning platforms among students in Educational Technology.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What are the types of e-learning platforms available for use among Educational Technology students?
2. What is the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology?
3. What are the common challenges associated with use of e-learning platforms among students in Educational Technology?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the responses of male and female students on the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology.

LITERATURE REVIEW

E-Learning, also referred to as online learning or electronic learning, utilizes information and communication technology to improve and facilitate education (Oye, Salleh & Lahad, 2012). According to Salehudin et al. (2021), E-learning encompasses group learning on social media platforms such as WhatsApp (WA), Telegram, Zoom, or other social media tools, enabling students to learn concurrently from different locations. E-learning is regarded as an innovative method for delivering educational services electronically, providing information that enhances students' knowledge, skills, and other learning outcomes (Fazlollahtabar uhammadzadeh, 2012). The E-learning system is executed through a network connection and involves utilizing information and communication technology via a computer (PC) or laptop connected to the internet (Horton & Horton, 2003). Furthermore, E-learning can be described as the process of learning on a computer (PC) or laptop linked to an internet connection.

Raouna (2023) identified several e-learning platforms:

- i. Udemy: Udemy aims to transform and democratize the educational landscape by enabling anyone to learn from its vast pool of more than 20000 experts. To a significant degree, Udemy has achieved its vision. This platform offers various content creation tools such as PDF documents, PowerPoint presentations, and others, allowing for the compilation of text and video content to create and publish courses.
- ii. Coursera: Recognized as one of the leading providers of massive open online courses, Coursera collaborates with universities and organizations globally to offer a wide range of in-depth courses, both paid and free, to learners worldwide. Coursera boasts one of the largest assortments of university partners, courses, specializations, and degree programs available.
- iii. LinkedIn Learning: Previously known as Lynda, LinkedIn Learning is a premier online learning platform that provides extensive courses and a library of tutorials spanning topics in business, creativity, and technology. This platform also offers both free and paid content created by experts, with courses available for beginners to advanced learners, resulting in certificates upon course completion. Other e-learning platforms such as Skillshare, edX, and Udacity also exist, each with their respective advantages and disadvantages (Raouna, 2023). These platforms can be utilized by higher education institutions as effective online learning solutions to fill the void left by traditional learning methods, such as in-person

meetings or classroom learning. Academic performance is an evaluation of student success across different academic subjects. This performance is influenced by factors including intellectual capability, personality, motivation, skills, interests, study habits, self-esteem, and the teacher-student relationship. A favorable result in students' academic performance indicates that the teaching and learning process was effective, with all other factors remaining constant. Olufemi (2018) noted that various factors, including students' learning abilities, parental backgrounds, peer influence, teacher quality, and learning resources, affect academic performance.

Strategies for Enhancing E-Learning Utilization in Higher Education Institutions

The role of technology is crucial in bolstering the professional skills of educators and their abilities in e-learning (Turvey, 2012). Instructors need to be competent in utilizing the technology provided by their institutions to facilitate the e-learning process. The role of the educator has evolved to be one of guiding students in their knowledge acquisition rather than simply imparting information; they must also consider the diverse aspects of student life, as not all learners are identical and require meticulous planning (Cavus, 2015). This suggests that instructors must leverage e-learning effectively to ensure that students can participate appropriately and successfully.

Additionally, social media has significantly contributed to the promotion of e-learning. Social media serves as a platform for individuals to connect with others from different countries and cultural backgrounds. Recently, platforms like Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram have gained immense popularity, especially among younger audiences (Salehudin et al., 2020). Utilizing social media as a medium for student learning has become a viable alternative (Lee et al., 2011). This is due to: First, the rapid advancement of science and technology, which has paralleled the increased usage of social media. Social media now functions not only as a communication tool (Lee et al., 2011) but also as a platform for educational purposes and business promotion. According to Zhan et al. (2015), universities can leverage social media to streamline the management of e-learning and provide knowledge to both staff and students. An educator might opt to incorporate social media into e-learning, believing it to be more user-friendly than specialized e-learning platforms like Easy Prep (Karkar et al., 2020).

Empirical Review

Allison et al. (2022) investigated the impact of e-learning on the academic performance of undergraduate students at Kebbi State University of Science and Technology using a descriptive survey methodology. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using mean and standard deviation techniques. The study's results indicated that e-learning positively influences the academic performance of undergraduate students at the institution. Based on these findings, the study recommended that the Kebbi state government should ensure high standards for institutions to acquire computer and internet facilities to improve the learning process within the university. Aboderin (2017) explored the effect of e-learning on the academic performance of distance learners at a Nigerian university, specifically using NOUN, Abuja, as the case study. This research employed a mixed-method approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative data collection. A questionnaire was used for quantitative data, while qualitative data were gathered through focus group discussions. Statistical analyses such as Spearman's correlation coefficient, ANOVA, T-test, and post-hoc tests were applied to the data. Findings indicated that various factors influenced students' academic performance, including ICT literacy, frequency of ICT engagement, marital status, previous academic achievements, daily internet usage, daily computer usage, and family size.

Fayomi et al. (2015) conducted a study to assess the effects of e-learning on academic performance among private secondary schools and tertiary institutions in Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria. The research utilized both primary and secondary data

sources. Structured and unstructured interviews were conducted with selected staff and students at the institutions, and questionnaires were distributed to students to gather insights about their experiences with e-learning. The research employed regression analysis to test a hypothesis aligned with the study's objectives. The findings indicate that e-learning significantly aids academic studies and personal development, leading to an enhanced learning experience and improved academic outcomes.

Nwakoby & Okoye (2020) investigated the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of students in tertiary institutions within Enugu State. A questionnaire was employed for data collection. The data was analyzed using regression analysis. The results showed that e-learning has a notable positive effect on the academic performance of students in tertiary institutions in Enugu, Nigeria, and it was recommended that the management of these institutions should provide sufficient resources for e-learning for their students. Utilizing structural equation modelling.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research design and it was considered suitable because the opinion of a representative sample of respondents was sought using questionnaire and the finding was generalized on the entire population. The participants of the study were drawn from students in the Faculty of Education, Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State and the sample size of 80 male and female students offering Educational Technology was selected from two (2) departments in the Faculty of Education, Alex Ekwueme Federal University, Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State using a purposive sampling technique. A self-structured questionnaires titled: E-Learning and Academic Performance Questionnaire (EAPQ) was developed, validated and used for the study. The instrument was a four-point response scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) with corresponding values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The instrument was face – validated by three experts: Two from Department of Educational Technology - AEFUNAI and one from Measurement and Evaluation Department- AEFUNAI. Their corrections and suggestions were utilized to improve the initial copies of the questionnaire to produce the final copies. Cronbach Alpha reliability method was adopted to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire items. A Cronbach Alpha coefficient of 0.83 was obtained and the collected data was analyzed using mean for research questions and t-test for the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Any mean response of 2.50 and above was considered agreed while any mean response below 2.50 was considered disagreed.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What are the types of e-learning platforms available for use among Educational Technology students?

Table 1: Mean rating of the responses of the respondents on the types of e-learning platforms available for use among Educational Technology students
 n = 80

S/N	Item statement	\bar{x}	SD	Rmk
1.	Micro Soft Teams e-learning platforms are utilized in your department.	3.31	.73	Agreed
2.	Technology and Internet facilities are available in my department to facilitate e-learning.	3.40	.64	Agreed
3.	Zoom e-learning platforms are utilized in your department	3.39	.63	Agreed
4.	Cousera is an interesting e-learning platform	3.31	.73	Agreed
5.	Mobile devices is available for improving students' academic performance in tertiary institution	3.28	.70	Agreed

6.	I utilize LinkedIn Learning to study online	3.26	.68	Agreed
7.	I have taken a course on Udemy E-learning platform	3.24	.76	Agreed

SD = Standard Deviation of the respondents and \bar{X} = Mean of the respondents

Data in Table 1 revealed that all the 7 items had their mean ratings ranging from 3.24 to 3.40 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed that the e-learning platforms identified are available for among use among educational technology students in Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State. The standard deviation of all the 7 items ranged from .63 to .76, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the e-learning platforms available for use among Educational Technology students, using Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State.

Research Question 2

What is the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology?

Table 2: Mean rating of the responses of the respondents on the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology

n = 80

S/N	Item statements	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	E-learning instruction makes teaching and learning easy	3.14	.79	Agreed
2	It reduces stress for both lecturers and students	3.13	.80	Agreed
3	E-learning instruction allows time and location flexibility	3.14	.79	Agreed
4	Online instruction is cost effective	3.14	.79	Agreed
5	It is time saving for both lecturers and students	3.34	.77	Agreed
6	E-learning instruction links distant learners and experts together to form an on-line collaborative learning community	2.84	.87	Agreed
7	E-learning instruction provides ultimate access to electronic learning materials both for lecturers and students	3.13	.80	Agreed
8	It guarantees quick and better access to the teaching Instructors	3.26	.68	Agreed
9	E-learning instruction helps student to acquire technology skills and have increased familiarity with technology.	3.24	.76	Agreed

SD = Standard Deviation of the respondents and \bar{X} = Mean of the respondents

Data in Table 2 revealed that all the 9 items had their mean ratings ranging from 2.84 to 3.26 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed that e-learning positively influences the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology in Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State. The standard deviation of all the 9 items ranged from .76 to .87, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology in Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State.

Research Question 3

What are the common challenges associated with use of e-learning platforms among students in Educational Technology?

Table 3: Mean rating of the responses of the respondents on common challenges associated with use of e-learning platforms among students in Educational Technology n = 80

S/N	Item statements	\bar{x}	SD	Decision
1	Incompetency among lecturers and students	2.65	.48	Agreed
2	Poor internet connectivity	2.72	.50	Agreed
3	Lack of technical support	2.95	.85	Agreed
4	Poor power supply	2.60	.49	Agreed
5	Government inability to enforce policy implementation	2.63	.58	Agreed
6	Lack of funds	3.18	.83	Agreed
7	Limited e-learning infrastructures	2.72	.50	Agreed
8	Lack of instructional time to effectively use e-learning tools	2.95	.85	Agreed

SD = Standard Deviation of the respondents and \bar{X} = Mean of the respondents

Data in Table 3 revealed that all the 8 items had their mean ratings ranging from 2.60 to 3.18 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed on the identified on the common challenges associated with use of e-learning platforms among students in Educational Technology in Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State. The standard deviation of all the 8 items ranged from .80 to .85, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the common challenges associated with use of e-learning platforms among students in Educational Technology, using Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State.

Hypothesis one

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the responses of male and female students on the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology

Table 4: t-test analysis of mean difference between male and female students on the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology

Gender	N	X	SD	Df	t-cal	α -value	Sig.	Decision
Male	47	2.89	.61	50	1.22	0.05	.063	Accepted H ₀₁
Female	33	2.70	.52					

Source: paired Samples t-test Result from SPSS

Data on table 4 shows that t-cal of 1.22, and a p-value of .063 which is greater than the level of significance 0.05 (p>.05). This result indicates that the hypothesis stated is accepted. With the forgoing, we therefore accept the null hypothesis for the items and reject the alternate hypothesis. Which means there is no significant difference between the mean responses

of male and female students on the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology, using Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The data presented in table 1 above revealed that all the 7 items had their mean ratings ranging from 3.24 to 3.40 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed that the e-learning platforms identified are available for use among educational technology students in Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State. The standard deviation of all the 7 items ranged from .63 to .76, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the e-learning platforms available for use among Educational Technology students, using Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State. This finding are in line with the findings of Ezeude et al (2021) who observed that a good number of e-learning platforms (Zoom, Microsoft Teams, Udemy, Coursera) have been utilized by undergraduates and there were recognized strategies (provision of more e-learning facilities and internet services) that should be adopted to improve the continuous utilization of e-learning platforms among undergraduates in Nnamdi Azikiwe University. Additionally, the findings relate to the revelation of Islam (2007) and Raouna (2023) who identified that the following are the e-learning platforms used by students: Udemy, Coursera, LinkedIn, Skillshare, edX and Udacity with their advantages and disadvantages. The researcher further stated that Zoom e-learning platforms, Microsoft Teams e-learning platforms, Technology and Internet facilities.

In table 2, the study revealed that all the 9 items had their mean ratings ranging from 2.84 to 3.26 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed that e-learning positively influences the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology in Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State. The standard deviation of all the 9 items ranged from .76 to .87, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the influence of e-learning on the academic performance of Students in Educational Technology in Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State. However, this finding is in agreement with the findings of Barker and Wendel (2001) who are of the view that students in virtual schools showed greater improvement than their conventional school counterparts in critical thinking, researching, using computers, learning independently, problem-solving, creative thinking, decision-making, and time management while (Benta et al, 2014) is also of the same view that e-learning creates an interactive environment for students to freely express themselves with more confidence than they do in a traditional classroom. The researchers noted that when students use e-learning platforms, it can enhance their confidence and ability to lead discussions, think critically to contribute productively or respond to given topics or discussions.

Findings on research question 3 revealed that all the 8 items had their mean ratings ranging from 2.60 to 3.18 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed on the identified common challenges associated with use of e-learning platforms among students in Educational Technology in Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State. The standard deviation of all the 8 items ranged from .80 to .85, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the common challenges associated with use of e-learning platforms among students in Educational Technology, using Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State. Furthermore, it connotes with the result of Allen & Seaman (2003) who revealed that one of these challenges of e-learning is inability of teachers to assist the students develop the ability and knowledge necessary

to make them use computer based studies effectively. They stated that in many computers based learning projects, students face some challenges of bad perception during their studies; lack of pedagogy in their curriculum, lack of user touch and feel in their computer based learning platform. The result also correlates with that of Adeosun and Maduekwe (2008) who recorded that Nigerian teachers and students could not demonstrate evidence of affective acquisition and use of ICT even at the basic skill level, hence they cannot fully utilize technology in their classrooms, though there is inadequate funding, limited ICT infrastructures and poor internet connectivity as it relates to online instruction.

CONCLUSION

From the insights and discussions presented, it can be inferred that e-learning platforms have had a markedly positive impact on the academic achievements of students studying Educational Technology at Alex Ekwueme Federal University Ndufu Alike, Ebonyi State. E-learning has transformed educational practices over the years by enhancing efficiencies, workflows, and collaborative efforts. The flexibility provided by e-learning regarding the location and timing of study allows educational programs to be implemented across teams around the globe. The incorporation of emerging technologies in the teaching and learning processes is now essential due to the evolving educational landscape, the increasing demand for flexible methodologies, and the necessity to boost creativity and productivity in learning.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the findings from this research, the following suggestions are proposed:

1. Social Networking Sites should be broadened, and new pages should be established to support academic initiatives and mitigate challenges in students' academic performance.
2. There is a necessity for the adoption and training related to all e-learning platforms for both students and educators to encourage ongoing use of e-learning platforms at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
3. Universities should provide and promote the availability of e-learning facilities and internet services to ensure the continued use of e-learning platforms within higher education institutions.
4. The government should implement backup generators and uninterruptible power supplies (UPS) to address the issue of inconsistent power supply, which is crucial for the effective use of electronic devices for e-learning.
5. Network providers ought to collaborate with the university administration to reduce data costs for both faculty and students, enabling them to upload and download educational materials for e-learning effectively.

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